

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

A New Image of the World or Philosophical Fragments

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Abstract

I present some sketches of ideas that are usually bothersome in the form of brief messages. They are somewhat similar to Zen koans, but only in respect to being the source that prompts the reader to improve, expand or destroy his personal reality.

Keywords: Heidegger; Kant; Reality; Imagination; Hieroglyphs; Plato; Nietzsche; Göbekli Tepe; Karahan Tepe; Yeshua; Siddhārtha Gautama.

1. Introduction.

When we are at the age when we begin to perceive the world with our senses and attempt to give it order within ourselves, we live a wonderful time where imagination reigns supreme, and where we can create incredible worlds. As our environment progressively fills our interior with truths and falsehoods, imagination begins to be restricted and the reality that we are creating begins to take over our endeavors. In the meantime, many have seen their reality destroyed by some monster, a reality that has been replaced by some deformed, shattered version not perceptible to us. As time passes, some fractures appear in personal reality (for example, discovering that Santa Claus is a lie). Some fractures are so small that we can cover them up, but others can remain as sores throughout life (the aforementioned monster creates them). And there are fractures that are 'sent' to the depths of oneself and forgotten due to their destructive effect. There are many people whose daily life consumes all their time and entire lives, dying after completing their life cycle as a human primate. But there are other people for whom the appearance of fractures in their momentary reality allows them to enter it and discover that there is something beyond the human primate, but it must be sought and found to have the reward for that search. In several of my previous reflections I tried to substantiate the thesis of the inherent inequality among human primates (in some regimes we are pontificated about presumed equality before the law, but we all know that those who have good money have the best lawyers).

Naturally, everything I have just said is what the various modifications and expansions of my reality have given me, a matter that I cannot prove or preach. I have presented some ideas of possible ways to pique the reader's curiosity so that they seek, find, and modify their own fractures to see what prize they obtain (1-12). Here I present some brief or very brief phrases in order to achieve the aforementioned effect.

2. To Shatter Realities

001. If the Greeks had known anything about the Western future, there would never have been a beginning of philosophy. Rome, Judaism, and Christianity completely transformed and adulterated the inceptive, i.e., Greek philosophy. That was written by Martin Heidegger, the greatest philosopher of the 20th century (German as usual). It is bad enough to have misunderstood him and to have flooded the world with dead trees turned into writings to make him seem like what he was not. Since it was discovered that Heidegger was indeed a National Socialist and anti-Semite

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(which was obvious to many), now the tree slaughter continues because let's say it frankly, the mob of 'philosophy writers' (who are not and will not be philosophers) continues to grow uncontrollably with I don't know what goal (13). On the other hand, we find the 'struggle for the poor Kant' between Germans and Russians, the former represented by a man who seems to love Oktoberfest beers and Schweinshaxe and the latter by an ex-spy who does not seem to understand the ultimate reasons for his famous 'special military operation'. Which Kant will be 'more Kant'? The German philosophers are already extinct and there are no European replacements. The Western philosophy is dead.

002. All human languages and dialects that existed or exist are of, and for primates. *Its function is to keep the species alive and functioning.* There are some attempts to create new terms to refer to some aspect of inner reality, but that doesn't seem to work simply because we lack a complete and clear description of that reality. That is why some of the thoughts presented here will necessarily be obscure and fragmentary and, at best, will have to make use of symbolism. *There is nothing that can be done about this at the moment, except to wait for a new Champollion.* I say this because Egyptian hieroglyphs can be read in different directions depending on the context and how they were inscribed. In many cases, hieroglyphs can be read from left to right, right to left, or even top to bottom, depending on the arrangement of the symbols and the direction in which the beings and animals depicted in them are facing. In addition, some texts can alternate the reading direction between lines or even within the same line (14). Perhaps minds can't all be read in the same way.

003. The reflections on 'I' are really the only ones I can write. *My observation that there are objects physically similar to me (bodies) cannot and could not lead me to conclude definitively that these objects contain within them something similar to what the 'external-object-I' contains.* When I use the term 'object' and 'content', I am not trying to establish a separation between something external and something internal, but I am trying to write something that the 'interior' of some other similar object can read and perhaps use for reflection. *That is on the assumption that what is inside the other object is somewhat similar to what is inside mine.*

004. When I 'traveled inside my mind' reading The Thousand and One Nights I marveled at palaces and caves full of gold and silver bars, sacks full of pearls, precious stones, gold and silver coins, mythical beings, incredible geographical places, etc. The core of the Arabian Nights is of Persian and not Arabic origin. The two volumes of René Khawam's edition should be read (R.K. Khawam, editor. The Arabian Nights. Edhasa, Barcelona, 2010). I was stunned reading Dr. Madrus's edition (J.C. Madrus, The Book of a Thousand Nights and One Night, El Ateneo, Buenos Aires, 1950, three volumes). In this latest edition the curious reader will find in the story called The Keys of Destiny (788th Night, Volume III), a masterpiece of alchemical symbolism. I think it's so visible that you can't see it. *These stories sometimes have incredible basis in the real world.* In the temple of Sree Padmanabhaswamy, located in the territory ruled by the Maharajas of Travancore, the underground vaults have been opened and a treasure has been found that can certainly be described as fabulous. Examples: a golden statue of the god Vishnu encrusted with emeralds, diamonds and rubies, a gold chain six meters long and weighing 37 kilos to adorn it, sacks filled with diamonds, pearls, gold and silver coins, etc. *But all of this becomes minuscule when compared to a place with an almost completely unexplored geography. This place has exuberant jungles populated with all kinds of animals, birds, and fishes. And it also has dark places and hells populated by terrifying creatures. This place is our interior (Urbs subterranea).*

005. In the West, we can jump from Plato's thought to Nietzsche's without any problems. *The whole interval between the two of them is nothing more than classification, labeling, self-consistent but vacuous constructs, solidification, stratification, and finally decay.* I won't deny that I love Plotinus. It is at the interface between East and West that the other way of access continues to manifest itself. The Gnostic Gospel of Thomas is a good example (Gospel of Thomas, Coptic text of Nag Hammadi. 'But if you do not know yourselves, you are mired in poverty and you are poverty itself', 'Show me the stone which the masons have rejected; this is the cornerstone', 'he who is knowledgeable of everything, but fails in himself, fails in everything', 'I am the light that is above them all. I am the universe: the universe has arisen from me and has come to me. Break a log and there I am; lift up a stone and there you will find me.') Quite a wasted invitation. They may seem like Zen koans, but they are only written in a way that our mind can no longer 'apprehend' (and not learn).

006. I declare myself a supporter of several sects. The most important of these are the Half-Empty Vessel Sect and the Forest Sect. The latter recognizes that trees make up the forest but gives primacy to the forest. I refuse to waste my life studying tree number 1,598,490. This, happily, has saved me from becoming a specialist. Certainly, it is extremely necessary to take a fair look at many trees since the forest is made up of different types of trees. *That's why there are two sides to the coin.*

007. Knowledge, detailed or not, about many things is the material that populates our 'interior'. Since 'nothing is produced from nothing', the less populated our 'interior' is, the more primates we are. Just look at the products of the

combination (morning shows + soap operas + reality shows + pamphlets + Dionysian scratch 'music'). By the way, the fault does not lie with the products but with the producers of that garbage. Products were created and indoctrinated for that: think less, work harder, and blow up when you're no longer useful.

008. Here are some topics that I was not able to fully develop. The fundamental core of all this is the following idea. As Desmond Morris said '*we are upright apes and not fallen angels*'(15). This is the 'formal' method as Pascal had placed the human primate halfway between beasts and angels. Brizendine adds that '*biology represents the underpinnings of our personalities and behavioral tendencies*'(16). These two assertions are not to be discussed, but to be accepted, almost as an axiom, and to draw from them all the conclusions and public policies that arise from them. *For example, politics itself, instead of being the practice of a small group of apes who are often parasites, liars, and scoundrels, should simply be scientifically applied biology (which would theoretically prevent such a group from being created)*. Hence the need to move quickly towards a complete knowledge of human genetics (a matter of time) and the techniques to be able to manipulate it backwards and forwards.

Those who find such a vision depressing have not noticed the most momentous fact that we have not finished 'standing upright.' But this process is cephalic in nature, and a simple glance at the environment or the use of some time for the study of history shows that *not everyone rises at the same speed*. Many tribal groups, ethnicities, groups within societies, etc., maintain a remarkable primate degree in their behavior. *This is an open field for the practitioner of the exact sciences who is not afraid of the system within which he lives and who knows how to formulate the correct scientific questions that can be subjected to hard contrast. In this way much new knowledge can be extracted from the shadows of ignorance.*

It is possible that an example of what makes us stand up more and more is this one (still under discussion for lack of more scientific knowledge). The human TKTL1 gene has been found to produce greater neurogenesis in the frontal neocortex of modern human primates than in Neanderthals and older relatives. And this could be the cause of our prevalence over them. And I note that some present-day human primates possess the Neanderthal version of the TKTL1 gene. The process of standing up can certainly open up new forms of perception unattainable to those who have been 'left behind'.

That's where we're going, step by step.

For the time being this is our week:

Sleep-wake up-eat-work/study-eat-work/study-eat-sleep.

Sleep-wake up-eat-work/study-eat-work/study-eat-coitus-sleep.

Sleep-wake up-coitus-eat-work/study-eat-work/study-eat-sleep.

Sleep-wake up-eat-work/study-eat-work/study-eat-sleep (Friday).

Sleep-wake up-eat-work/study-eat-work/study-eat-drink/play/eat-drink/coitus-drink/etc.-coitus-drink/etc-coitus.....-sleep (Friday-Saturday).

Sleep-awakening-cook-eat- leisure/play-eating- leisure/play-eat-leisure/jugar-coitar-drinking/etc.-coitus-drinking/etc.-coitus-coitus-drinking/etc.-coitus-coitus-coitus.....-sleep (Saturday-Sunday).

.....

Sleep-wake up-eat-work-eat-work-eat-sleep (and take care of the babies).

It is the daily and repetitive life of the human primate in the period of ignorance.

.....

You are just an average man, with an average life

You work from nine to five; hey hell, you pay the price

All you want is to be left alone in your average home

.....

Again:

Formally, we are the product of intercourse between a male and a female belonging to the order of Primates, which may have been long or short, boring or exciting, wanted or not, etc. And it may have come in a multiplicity of places and forms (when I was younger, much younger, I asked for more precise facts about myself, but I only got a fairly long reprimand, as befitted those times). The rest I sum up by quoting a song: "*You know when you're born / You first see light of day / Through a gap in your mother's legs / It's the truth / And from that minute on / Most of us guys / And some of you girls spend your life / Trying to get back into a hole / But, don't worry / Because if you make it / If you don't make it / They're gonna dig a hole for you eventually in the ground / And slot you right back to Mother Earth*". That's how it has been, that's how it is, and that's how it will be for the time being (Eric Burdon & War: Blues for Memphis Slim).

009. Someone asked: Are we worms because a billion years ago worms were among our ancestors? If we don't find a human primate that has the same internal life as a worm, the answer should be no. But there is no doubt that we are primates. Anatomically modern *Homo sapiens* (including mestizos and 'pure' sapiens) must have already possessed what I will call 'successions' in terms of their daily lives. *And what would have been the daily life of an anatomically modern sapiens some 300,000 years ago?* The list is short: sleeping, feeding, making or keeping a fire, reproducing, making tools, fighting for their position within the group, taking care of their progeny (?). In short: survive in order to propagate the species. The New Man or the Übermensch, who has not yet appeared in public, will overcome this.

010. Definition. An anatomically modern human primate (today) is a specimen that performs a number of complex daily activities which, when analyzed in their essence, show that they are only intended for the same goals as the first anatomically modern *Homo sapiens*, the first members of the genus *Homo*, the Australopithecines, etc.: to live to survive and propagate the species through the creation and maintenance of a '*sphere of comfort*'. The 'closest' sphere is sphere 0, where one maneuvers for food, housing, marriage plans, reproduction, offspring education, security threats, etc., and is fiercely created and defended, even if unconsciously. Think of the herds of herbivores of the African savannah and their spheres of comfort. The weakest are always on the periphery. There are other major spheres that encompass many 0 spheres. The largest of these is the (local) sphere called the 'country'. A little mental exercise on the part of the reader will make him see how many spheres surround him and how many of them were made by himself. These spheres are primate (especially sphere 0), and many will defend them at all costs and even accept any kind of political regime that guarantees their integrity. *When the biological basis of this phenomenon is fully understood, it will be possible to study it with the exact sciences.*

011. And what is 'the' science supposed to be? According to the RAE, science is the '*body of knowledge obtained through observation and reasoning, systematically structured and from which general principles and laws are deduced with predictive capacity and experimentally verifiable*'. We must add the obligation to use the scientific method(17) and the rigorous testing(18, 19). *Of course, if we take the term 'science' (from the Latin scientia, from scire, 'to know') in its broadest sense and forget about the scientific method and hard testing, we can create Culinary Science, Legal Sciences, Social Sciences, Astral Science and other 'sciences' that only merit that some of them be considered at most as 'Studies' and others as pseudoscience or anti-science.*

012. Not so long ago we were told that in Spain it was necessary to tie the leg of a nun with a rope to the stone columns of the convent so that it would not go back to the stratosphere due to its 'sanctity'. There were also reports of fakirs enchanting ropes so that their assistant would climb them and disappear on some 'higher plane'. We've heard thousands of accounts of UFO sightings. Curiously, the appearance of the camera made the first two phenomena disappear. UFOs, thanks to the billions of cell phones that record images, videos and sounds, are entering the path of disappearance (let's recognize that there are still atmospheric phenomena that remain to be explained). But there is still an extremely dangerous subgroup of human primates who profit from their ability to manipulate many who are weaker than them and fulfill the saying that in the land of the blind the one-eyed man is king: they are the sellers of illusions that offer us philosophical, political, economic, religious paradises, etc. They are very dangerous because they appear with an aura of false modesty, with seemingly laudable purposes, dressed in the ermine robe of virtue, etc. Closer inspection reveals that their appearance is infinitely superior to their real worth and that, in essence, they do not remain in the truth because there is no truth in them. When they speak lies, they speak of themselves, because they are liars and fathers of lies. *However, a deeper analysis reveals the evolutionary advantage of these clusters.* They are made up solely of human primates that have discovered, consciously or unconsciously, a novel group way of living in order to live or survive, to propagate the species and nothing else. For example, one of the strategies of several of them is to put their hand in your pocket to empty it and they also make you like that real assault (they are called the 'percentage robbers' because they decimate your pocket). If we want to waste some of our time and carefully examine their daily work, we will check it out. *These are the two-dimensional human primates, whose life is but one educational experience after another and who receive death as a graduation diploma. They are at a slightly different level (not higher) than one-dimensional human primates.*

013. The human primate is in full evolution and, so to speak, waiting for the species that will replace it by hook or by crook (if this happens it will be by force without a doubt). But, unfortunately, we have two things that the members our direct and collateral family did not have. *I am not exaggerating when I say that none of the individuals of the species that inhabited Africa two million years ago 'thought' about matters such as 'when will I become extinct?' or 'which species will evolve from me?'. We can do it. And, as scientific knowledge advances, we might even stop our physical evolution and remain Homo sapiens (I think the only exception to this will be when we can, if ever, leap to the stars: happily the space-time separation will cause different groups of colonizers to evolve differently).* And what might be the nature of future evolutionary changes in the present-day human primate? From a physical point of view, we could end up losing our hair in some areas or perhaps what is left of a vestigial tail. Teilhard de Chardin seems to have hit the nail on the head

when he suggests increasing cephalization. He make a mistake, and this is because his thinking is rigidly framed by his particular religious beliefs (like the blinders on horses), when he speaks of a growing convergence towards the Omega point or of a growing perfection of the nervous systems. What we need is for science to clearly define and quantify what is to be understood by '*increasing cephalization*'. But for that we need scientists with a little more cephalization than usual.

014. The billions of human primates can be envisioned as constituting a swamp from which, every so often, will-o'-the-wisps emerge. Those will-o'-the-wisps are those human primates called 'the dark heroes' who have commanded peoples and led them towards an auspicious or inauspicious destiny: those dark heroes who always bear armor and swords stained with blood. They are also those human primates who created and propagated the first knowledge and the first structures at various points. Let us clearly establish the following here. *The transcendental advances of human history have never been due to the 'masses', which can only be considered (I repeat) as the humus, the substrate, the manure, the gene pool, etc. upon which the new biological varieties will bloom that, if perpetuated, will improve the average quality of the substrate.* That cycle will repeat itself to the extent that historical circumstances permit it. The masses that were supposed to create the New Man ended up in the various gulags as slaves of the defenders of the workers. Today's Western masses are well described by Gentile(20) and by Fontana(21).

015. It has been suggested that in some cases symbols have lost their connection to inner life and that, in many cases, everything has been transformed into mummified and meaningless rituals. My interpretation is different. For the human primate, lacking clear vision, it is impossible to grasp the symbol and its multiple possible meanings within a given context unless they become fully aware of such incapacity and take action to evolve internally. In the meantime, they must live with symbols and rituals that are crude, cardboard-like, and empty while believing they have attained something. For some, this serves only to obtain power, money, and an alleged predominance over their 'worshippers.'

016. Sixty-six billion neutrinos pass through every square centimeter of skin of every person on Earth each second. They pass through the human body and through the Earth without colliding with anything. And no one marvels. But if I mention 'soul' or 'spirit' there is garment-rending without even asking what I mean by it.

017. I believe it was Foucault who said that 'they permit individuals to effect by their own means or with the help of others a certain number of operations on their own bodies and souls, thoughts, conduct, and way of being, so as to transform themselves in order to attain a certain state of happiness, purity, wisdom, perfection, or immortality.' There can be no revelation without renunciation. Exomogenesis takes its model from martyrdom, which is a killing of oneself. Epicurus, in his Letter to Menoecus, says it is never too early or too late to occupy oneself with the soul's salvation, since there are souls that perish and souls that reach the level where they know what to do in order not to die.

018. There are even circumstances in which argumentation loses its promising appearance and becomes an obstacle to progress (this was said by someone I cannot recall).

019. Specialist: One who cultivates or practices a particular branch of a discipline, an art, or a science. To be called this is considered by some blind ones a compliment and by others a grave insult. This specimen has the bad habit of speaking even about that which they do not know.

020. Many years ago, I was re-reading fragments of some pre-Socratics in an attempt to incorporate them into a course. Arduous work. The following year, and purely by chance, I returned to them during a reading of Popper, which led me to an interesting work by Feyerabend. These brief outbursts are the results of bringing the water to my own mill without needing to leave the neighbors' dry. Every 'complex' human primate goes through stages in their inner development. Let us consider Nietzsche, who transits from an almost unbearable academic pedantry to heights of thought inaccessible to most human primates. It was during this work that I discovered Antisthenes (Philosophy consists more in the manner of conducting oneself).

021. The more radical versions of the practical implementation (in the style of Ancient Greece) of the precept "a sound mind in a sound body" include forced sterilization and medical euthanasia (this is a softer version of the Mount Taygetus). That, on one hand. Now on the other. There is no reason that precludes the possibility that, if the swamp is allowed to populate itself with all possible varieties (including those that require assistance their entire lives to survive), some combination may occur that gives rise to some improved variety. For the moment, it appears this latter possibility is the one that must be maintained at all costs. However, results are expected soon because we risk having more overpopulation that has nothing new to contribute.

022. Subject X is standing on a sidewalk at a midpoint between two corners. He sees a vehicle coming from his left at a very high speed. He looks to his right and sees the traffic light at the corner change from green to yellow. He calculates. 'It won't be able to brake and may crash.' He continues watching. Finally, the vehicle collides with another. Subject Y is standing at the intersection of the streets where the aforementioned traffic light is located. He looks to his left and sees a vehicle coming down the street at a very high speed. He looks ahead and sees another vehicle coming down that other street at a very high speed. He looks at the traffic light and sees it change from green to yellow. He calculates. 'They're going to crash.' They crash. *This is a good example to understand why one must view things from different perspectives and why some visions are broader than others. Regarding the latter, almost no one has them. That is why we are where we are.*

023. Dodds (22). Using the blinkers of 'this-is-how-I-know-it', we can underestimate or completely overlook certain types of experiences to which we no longer attribute any religious meaning. My question: Can we, for example, know with certainty the reason(s) that hunter-gatherers (assuming they were such) had 12,000 years ago to construct Göbekli Tepe or Karahan Tepe, or that Neanderthals had 176,000 years ago to construct the structures in the Bruniquel cave? The answer is that we cannot and will not be able to. *And we call this absolute ignorance "religious structures." In any case, this is more probable than suggesting UFO parking lots or extraterrestrial camping sites.*

024. Heidegger tells us this: *"The two thousand five hundred years that separate us from Heraclitus are a dangerous thing. Our interpretation of the fragments of Heraclitus, in order to see something here, requires the most energetic self-criticism. On the other hand, it also requires a certain audacity. One must risk something, because otherwise one has nothing in hand. Thus, there is nothing to object to a speculative interpretation."* Here is my speculation. Heraclitus descended from Androcles, founder of Ephesus and son of Codrus, king of Athens. He would have been king had he not renounced in favor of his brother. The royal family of Ephesus maintained the prerogative of the priesthood of Demeter Eleusinian, which strongly suggests that Heraclitus must have been initiated into one or more Mysteries. We know that Heraclitus is said to have become a misanthrope and went to live in the mountains, where he ate herbs and plants. Question: Why did he decide to do this? If we add to this that he was arrogant towards anyone and disdainful, we could suppose that for some reason he had come to despise people. This arrogance is not that which could come from his social status, since in fragment 103 he tells us that *"it is more necessary to extinguish arrogance than a fire."* Regarding what he wrote, the Pseudo-Aristotle of De Mundo treats him as "Heraclitus the Obscure" and Diogenes Laertius tells us that according to some he wrote in an obscure way so that only the capable would have access to him and that he would be despised by the vulgar. Question for the reader: Why, if he wanted to write, did he do so in a presumably obscure way? Answer: because he knew that some would understand him.

025. Other fragments: *"The god whose oracle is at Delphi neither utters nor conceals but gives signs." "Asses would prefer straw to gold." "Pigs take more pleasure in mud than in pure water."* I know many asses and a multitude of pigs.

026. Someone elegantly stated that Nietzschean thought has been obscured by 'generations' of theoreticism. It was especially mutilated by minds that, being unable to understand the philosopher's soul because they did not possess something similar capable of assimilating his thought, produced a flat Nietzsche resembling an ape through the 'projection' of their own essence. Poor Friedrich! You have been the object of endless masturbatory acts. The worst of all are those produced by writers who did not possess the 'Germanic soul' capable of comprehending you. Is what I am saying not clear? I could not lead a group of musicians who were inhabitants of, for example, the New Guinea rainforest or the Brazilian Mato Grosso to perform some of their folk music. Certainly I could conduct them, but I would never obtain a work that conveys the soul of those peoples because I cannot incorporate into the performance something I do not have. Hence the need to, for example, correctly choose which works of European classical music to listen to (conductor, orchestra, choirs with a 'European soul').

027. It is interesting to know that, in the worst case, and as I write these lines, a great number of viruses, bacteria, protozoans, and fungi inhabit and feed on me, both on and within me. Let us examine the problem of the enclosure itself, which defines me in front of other enclosures and represents the physical correlate of the concept that is my name: Juan Sebastián. I have wondered in what ways Juan Sebastián could cease to be Juan Sebastián. Before that, I will analyze the veracity of the statement that my enclosure has perfectly defined physical limits. I look at my arm and body and visually ascertain that there seems to be a surface (the skin?) that appears to be the boundary between my enclosure and the other. But I know that, for example, between the hairs of my forearm and the forearm, and between the hair of my head and my head, there is air. Will it be 'mine/part of me' or not? To avoid complicating matters too much, I will assume that an interface exists that comprises all those elements. But there is a vast region worth investigating. Its entries/exits comprise, in the cranial sector, the auditory system with the Eustachian tube, the nasal cavities, and the mouth. In the lower cranial sector and thorax, that region extends into the pharynx and larynx. From there, that system diverges into two major pathways. The first goes, via the trachea, to the lungs. The second is defined by the esophagus, stomach, and

intestines, ending at the anus. The surface area of that region is truly large and defines a large volume as well. Well, now I wonder if everything that exists within that volume (air, fluids, food, waste, etc.) is 'mine/part of me' or not? Does the bile that exits into the intestine remain part of me? These questions are necessary if one has the pretension of constructing the intension of a *Homo sapiens* and determining its unequivocal notes. *Since I do not have a definitive answer, I will have to examine another day the problem of determining when Juan Sebastián ceases to be Juan Sebastián.*

028. An examination of certain literature clearly shows that its authors, despite their limited intellectual reach, mediocre style, and the unconscious complicity of vulgar and ignorant people, know how to present their theses in such a way that it aligns with the interests of a broad public (and simultaneously fill their pockets). Evidently, one does not expect to find in that galaxy of quarrelsome types at least some specimen capable of presenting in a dignified manner one or more arguments that sustain their theses. There is no doubt that there are clear manifestations of an intellectual menopause that leaves one astonished. At the very least, I expected to read some elaborate arguments that would fill me with wonder and have me reflecting for a good while. But this was not the case. I called them 'reptiles,' not because I want to be offensive toward them (as this would allow them to continue writing nonsense), but simply because of their extremely primitive and foolish reasoning. Among them are those who washed Nietzsche and Heidegger with 'Ordinarien' brand detergent to leave them aseptic and 'edible' for the groups that were the targets of their scorn.

029. My Dear one. It was such your hurry to write a text that would describe the Universal Library in such a marvelous way that its mere reading would propel the spirit of some towards indescribable heights, that you forgot to include several details that were also mentioned in the manuscript that I provided you. As several inconsistencies have been noticed from time to time by some readers due to your inaccuracies and omissions, here I comment on the most important ones for a future edition (the most complete description I know of the Library is in the corresponding volume of the First Encyclopedia of Tlön). *The Library is large, really very large, perhaps monstrously large, but not infinite.....*

1. (5 bookshelves) × (32 books per bookshelf) = 160 books per wall and (160 books per wall) × (4 walls per gallery) = 640 books per gallery. 2. Since the number of galleries is unknown, it is necessary to calculate the total number of books as follows: 1 book = (410 pages) × (40 lines) × (80 letters) = 1,312,000 orthographic symbols. 3. Then, the 25 orthographic symbols can be ordered in 25 ways, which is 251,312,000.... You know the accursed connotation possessed by the number 1,312,000 (see the *Liber de Angelis et Daemonibus*). It would have been enough to include a single extra orthographic symbol to avoid the punishment.....

[Note from this author. The description of the architectural structure of the Library was not entirely accurate. Jonathan Millen, in his Gallery Layout in Borges' *Library of Babel*, noted some very important discrepancies].

030. Isolate yourself and try to think for two hours without falling asleep. If you cannot, you should be concerned. Try it for one hour. If you cannot, this is serious. Try it for half an hour. If you cannot, this is very serious. *After the age of 40, this deficiency has no solution.*

031. We all suffer, to a greater or lesser degree, from political, religious, philosophical, etc. superstitions that force us to see things not as they are (is this possible?), but as we are (from an evolutionary point of view, no doubt some need those superstitions to 'understand', influence and control their sphere of comfort). A large part of that heavy baggage is placed on us when we are still defenseless, either because we are at the stage where we still do not manage the language (some never will) or in the later stage of mental defenselessness (it is in this stage that certain forms of behavior are recorded in you, Santa Claus, the stork of babies, religion and other nonsense from which it is possible to happily free oneself later, although it costs quite a bit and not everyone can do it). *This occurs in the parent-child chain and is not something for which parents should be censured, since almost all are inexorably doomed to do it. But many of those imprints have consequences, some of them very serious. Many of them lead some to make some incorrect choices.*

032. In any case, it must be said that it is this entire poisonous maladjustment that blinds us, prevents a clear mental attitude, and prevents us from seeing part of the panorama. *The cleaning out of all that mental garbage is what allows a more panoramic vision.*

033. Many years ago in Santiago, Chile, it was extremely rare to own a private car. When I was able to have one, I devoted myself to local tourism and traveled almost the entire city. The best route was around the entire Santiago, traveling along the only ring road that existed. As the kilometers passed, changes in the socioeconomic situation could be appreciated, from mansions to social housing blocks where the poor accumulated. One day I commented at my job that I had gone to the XX neighborhood which, according to the media, was swimming in delinquency. A colleague was horrified: They could have robbed or killed you! she told me. Apart from being the perfect example of a prejudice created

by lack of information and the human mania for labeling things, people and situations, that trip clearly showed me that a simple separation of a few kilometers can create completely different worlds. I remember an old lady who called us aliens and who suffered enormously from having to share her privileges.

034. Once, while examining in detail the new memory banks to which he had gained access, 'Y' felt deep within himself that he had done something incorrect when he was still naive and when he did not know that what he had done was incorrect. Intrigued and uncomfortable, he searched in his memory bank called 'isolated garbage from myself' for some political, economic, philosophical, ethical, moral, etc., etc., etc. explanation that would justify what he had felt and found nothing. After several days he discovered that this discomfort had to be appeased by acknowledging the incorrectness. *That day he knew that something new had already formed inside him that brought him a little closer to the exit of Plato's Cave.*

035. 'X' related the following dream. 'I saw myself in a small, closed room with no doors except a small opening located at the top of one of the walls. Some spiders appear and I begin to kill them one by one. However, the last one manages to escape through the opening.' Quite a delicacy for scholars of the garbage dump(s) inside human primates (the Freudians and similar birdbrains). Sometime later, 'X' will remember, during a magnificent experience of those that last around 8 hours, that he lay in his crib when he saw a 'monstrous' spider standing on his chest. When consulted, his family told him that it had been a tiger spider and that this had happened when he was around a year and a half old. After that, he lost his fear of spiders and only pardoned the lives of tiger spiders. This is a prime example of an imprint that is difficult to get rid of. Regarding the garbage can, the exact sciences have not yet been able to formulate the questions (hypotheses) that need to be asked in order to finally shed light on that absolutely obscure terrain and incorporate it into scientific knowledge. *The other day he dreamed of the spider that escaped long ago.*

036. The best doughs I know are the ones used to make empanadas. The masses, the authentic masses (the populace), do not make history. At most, they are used and made to believe that they are the ones who decide. It is always one or perhaps a few ones. When an *Australopithecus afarensis* manufactured the first stone tool more than 3 million years ago, it was a single individual who was perhaps observed by others. The most capable copied him, the technique was distributed, and we employed it for almost 3.2 million years, with improvements and new uses probably. We will not be able to know how many 'advances' occurred during those times and were forgotten due to lack of imitators or the inventor's death.

037. When 'X' asked himself 'Why is it so difficult to grow up?', he realized that he was over 40 years old and that he was still growing. And he noticed that others were no longer growing.

038. On the morning of January 3, 1889, while Nietzsche was walking in Turin, he witnessed a coachman beating a horse. He threw his arms around the horse's neck and then collapsed on the ground, losing consciousness. Other variants have been told. I believe that this observation finally illuminated Friedrich in such a way that he stopped speaking through his brain. This topic is the most important problem of 19th century European philosophy (opinion). No one has contributed something decent to read, with a film about the horse's fate being the worst contribution to this matter.

039. The Ship of Fools or the Ship of the Foolish? Here we are today, faithfully carrying out the process of transvaluation of values (Nietzsche thought that the pinnacle of that process had occurred with the triumph of the populist Platonism, a matter that does not seem to be clarified yet) and with the rapid creation of the human primate for which 'being' is, or being available to be manipulated or exploited, or being a manipulator and exploiter of other human primates. Happily and unhappily, the human primates who hold the power (the real one) to wipe out the sapiens species seem to have embarked, either on the ship of fools or on the ship of the mad. It already seems too late to be able to remove them from the helm. This, if true, steers the ship towards a major catastrophe that seems biologically necessary and that incidentally includes global warming. Will we end up in a dystopian world in which natural selection has favored the most idiotic, because they reproduce more? I took that last sentence from some comments about the movie 'Idiocracy' which shows a future dominated by idiots.

Figure 1 The Ship of Fools (Sebastian Brant, 1494).

Figure 2 The Ship of Nuts (Hieronymus Bosch, 1504)

040. Are we all like the Ship of Theseus? Answering that question definitively is impossible due to lack of knowledge and lack of primates who decide to seek some answer. In reality, it seems that it can never be answered due to lack of neurons.

041. The wind blows / leaves fall / branches shine / in the light of dawn ...

The chariot of fire is born / happiness overflows me / Love / did you visit me, and I did not know it? ... (That day was tragic and empty).

042. On a sunny day with a clear blue sky,

Love arrived stealthily, without fanfare.

Soft whispers, laughter in the air,

But I, immersed in life, did not notice.

Captivating smile, ardent gaze,

Love circled me, following its current.

Cupid launched his invisible arrows,

But my heart, oblivious, inaccessible.
I strolled in a world of routine and haste,
While Love sought me without haste.
In every touch, in every furtive encounter,
Its presence went unnoticed, elusive.
Until one starry night, in silence,
Love touched my soul with its influence.
I awoke, at last, to its passionate embrace,
And understood it had always been by my side.
Oh, day when Love visited me without warning,
Pardon my distraction, for not being precise.
I thank its patience, its constant love,
And in its eternal fire, I now burn, a lover.
(Only those who have loved until their heart aches will fully understand this).

043. The increasingly complex words and languages have allowed us to begin to better master matter, but they are like a veil. *It is a pity that almost everyone has lost the ability to 'see' behind that veil.*

044. Nietzsche wrote this in *The Gay Science* (GS 116): "*Herd Instinct. Wherever we encounter a morality, we find an estimation and hierarchy of human drives and actions. These estimations and hierarchies are always the expression of the needs of a community and a herd: what is most beneficial to it first, and second and third, is also the highest measure for the value of all individuals. With morality the individual is instructed to be a function of the herd and to attribute value to himself only as a function. Since the conditions for the preservation of a community have been very different from those of another community, there have been very different moralities; and with regard to the essential transformations that will have to occur in herds and communities, in states and societies, one can prophesy that there will still be very divergent moralities. Morality is the herd instinct in the individual.*" This matter of the herd made me investigate the distribution of dominant and weak animals in African herds. In the case of herds of zebras and antelopes, the dominant males tend to position themselves more towards the center of the herd, while the juveniles and females are more on the periphery. This gives them better protection against predators (this has been observed in plain and mountain zebras). In impala herds, the dominant females position themselves in the center along with the young, while the subordinates are on the edges. In the case of wildebeest herds, it was found that the dominant males position themselves more towards the center, allowing them better access to females. The weak, sick or young are on the periphery. In the case of buffalo herds, the dominant males walk in the center to be better protected. These are the evolutionary advantages of the dominants. But in the case of human primates, this distribution is not similar in many cases. Given the great biological differences among human primates, the case typified as 'in the land of the blind, the one-eyed man is king' can occur. Taking advantage of various weaknesses (the weak frogs asking for a king to enjoy protection and perks), we have some 'one-eyed' individuals who position themselves in positions of power where they use and abuse it. There are always cases in plain sight. That is why we are where we are.

045. In Nietzsche's late notebooks from 1888, more specifically in Notebook W II 5 [71], this phrase appears: '*The biological isotherm of an organism expresses the fact that it strives to restore all the rhythmic disturbances provoked in it by external influences until it achieves its normal measure.*' My opinion is that biological isotherms exist in the human primate. The main ones serve as boundaries between what one was, what one is, and what one will be, and in the primate who feels drawn toward the exit of Plato's cave, those boundaries are mobile.

046. Saturn Devouring His Children. *That manifests itself in authentic revolutions when they devour their own children.* That was said by Pierre Victor Vergniaud, guillotined during the period of the French Revolution called 'The Terror'.

047. Unfortunately there will always be, and possibly will continue to be, a large percentage of the human population that tells itself stories about our origin based on all kinds of superstitious beliefs. Example: a 2014 Gallup poll shows that 42% of the population of the American Empire believes that God created us in our present form, 31% that humans evolved with God guiding us, and only 19% that we simply evolved. This is a dangerous people due to their extreme ignorance. This is regarding the human primate. It only remains to add that, given that this primate has taken its stupidity to the limit of believing that the Earth belongs to it and not that it belongs to the Earth, it is to be expected that the species that succeeds us evolutionarily will dispose of us as quickly as possible. In any case, this insolence and arrogance will cost us dearly. Task to exercise and meditate on. See if this (modified) phrase from Ursula K. Le Guin applies or not to a real world: "We must try to raise the level of the human gene pool, which is nothing more than a filthy puddle since the population explosion."

048. Every so often and in certain places, 'unique beings' have appeared who have tossed golden peanuts to the ignorant human primates in their surroundings. A good but futile attempt: some are murdered, and others end up disillusioned. Yeshua, in the little or nothing we have of him (modified, adulterated, censored, etc.), grows bored of trying to make his disciples (a group of ignorant fishermen) understand something of what he says. Nothing. The other thing worth mentioning is this: only after spending 40 days in the desert with himself does he decide to preach. Around 600 years before him, Siddhārtha Gautama embarked on a similar path. But, unlike Yeshua, he left a practical teaching for those human primates who he knew could not attain his state. He taught a Middle Way between sensual indulgence and severe asceticism. His core teachings are summarized in the Four Noble Truths and the Noble Eightfold Path. If you drink from that source and are still thirsty, then seek 'beyond'. After the disappearance of those 'unique beings', peanut sellers appear (without gold) who self-declare themselves to be the bridge (with mandatory tolls included) to 'salvation'. They possess necklaces with countless colorful beads. And the human primate who only needs a walking stick for life ends up in the hands of greasy and ignorant primates who suck their blood and brains.

3. Conclusions

In several of my previous reflections I tried to substantiate the thesis of the inherent inequality among human primates (in some regimes we are pontificated about presumed equality before the law, but we all know that those who have good money have the best lawyers). But I am sure that the human primate daily reality can be questioned with the aid of the material presented above. Only when one or more readers communicate with me about these contents, the real value of these thoughts and of this paper will be available.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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